

A COMPARISON AMONG CORALLIGENOUS-BASED INDICES FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF THE MARINE ECOLOGICAL QUALITY

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Mediterranean coastal areas host the endemic biogenic reefs commonly known as “coralligenous”. They develop in dim-light conditions from about 20 m down to 120 m depth, shaped by bioconstructors, mainly represented by coralline algae, and erosive processes acted by borer organisms and physical abrasion. This dynamic equilibrium creates a morphologically complex calcareous substrate where highly diverse benthic assemblages develop, offering shelter and food to a rich community of vagile invertebrates and fishes. Hence, coralligenous reefs are real hotspots of biodiversity, affected by several anthropogenic and natural pressures that threaten their structure and functioning. Despite the undeniable need to conserve coralligenous habitats, their extreme spatial variability and the operational restrictions imposed by scuba diving at depths where they usually develop limited the number of studies aimed at assessing their health status. Only recently, some coralligenous-based indices to evaluate marine ecological quality have been proposed. The Coralligenous Assemblage Index (CAI - Deter *et al.*, 2012), the Ecological Status of Coralligenous Assemblages (ESCA - Cecchi *et al.*, 2014) index, the COralligenous Assessment by ReefScape Estimate (COARSE - Gatti *et al.*, 2015) index and the Index-Cor (Sartoretto *et al.*, 2014) were compared among each other and against some classical univariate indices (e.g. the Shannon diversity Index) in 21 sites along the southern coasts of France.

The four coralligenous-based indices are built on different approaches and combining various metrics. The CAI and ESCA indices are both based on photographic sampling and image analysis; on the contrary, the COARSE index is based on direct *in situ* observations, while the Index-Cor integrates photos and direct observations. Image analysis methods differ among CAI, ESCA and Index-Cor. The metrics considered by the indices vary from the simple abundance of some taxa/groups, to the sensitivity of species to different pressures, to structural and functional metrics.

Results showed that the four indices are not always concordant in indicating the ecological quality of coralligenous habitats and costal waters, some metrics being more sensitive than others to the increasing pressure levels.